

DEVELOPMENT OF NUTRIENT AND HAIR GROWTH SPREY TECHNOLOGY

Turayeva S.S.¹

Abduqayumova S.B.²

¹Samarkand city Instructor of the Department of
Preclinical Sciences at Zarmed University

²Samarkand city Student of group 105 of the Faculty of
Pharmacy, Zarmed University

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Abstract. Hair loss is the physiological or pathological process of hair loss. Pathological hair loss leads to uniform thinning of hair, partial or total thinning in some areas, or complete baldness. The causes of hair loss can be vitamin and microelement deficiencies, drug side effects, hormonal and infectious diseases, stress, heredity, improper hair care. Often, eliminating these causes leads to hair restoration.

Although the causes of illness and hair loss are different, in both cases a person loses a large amount of hair. One of the most common causes of hair loss is a lack of iron in the body. Women often suffer from iron deficiency anemia due to natural menstrual blood loss during menstruation, and its first clinical manifestation is felt specifically in the nails, skin, and hair [1].

Hair loss of 60, 100 hairs per day is considered normal. That is, the hair fibers are renewed. However, excessive hair loss indicates the presence of some problems related to hair and requires immediate treatment, nutrition, and measures.

Keywords. Separator, spray, water-alcohol, technology, hair loss.

Rosemary reduces damage and scratching of the scalp and ensures fast and healthy hair growth. Moisturizes hair and reduces its electrification, gives hair a bright appearance, and improves hair quality.

Cleanses the scalp to prevent dandruff [2].

Pepper buds are known not only for their unique taste and aroma, but also for their medicinal properties. This spice has long been used in folk medicine for the prevention and treatment of diseases. The spice is a source of vitamins K, B₆ (pyridoxine), B-1 (thiamine), C, and riboflavin and is used for hair care.

It contains glycosides, proteins, vitamins, vitamin K, pantothenic acid; carotenoids; chlorophyll (2-5%), cytosterol, histamine, violaxanthin. The leaves are a unique multivitamin concentrate. Therefore, its leaves are also used in medicine for hair care, giving it a bright appearance and improving hair quality.

The leaves are a unique multivitamin concentrate. Therefore, its leaves are also used in medicine for hair care [3].

Purpose of scientific work: The purpose of this scientific work is to develop a spray technology that has anti-shedding and nourishing properties for hair.

Result. Rosemary, peppermint, nettle, vitamin B₁₂, nicotinic acid are components of the spray. The main active substances in the composition of plants were isolated by percolation with a 40% water-alcohol mixture (1:1). The composition and technology were developed by adding the above-mentioned vitamins to the obtained water-alcohol extract [4].

Conclusion. As a result of the research, a clear extract with a characteristic odor and a reddish-brown color was formed.

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